

Teaching Methodology and Use of Technology between China and Bangladesh: A Comparative Study

Sheikh Sultan Ahmed^{1*}, Kazi Nafisa Rasheed¹

¹School of Foreign Language and Literature, Nanjing Tech University, Jiangsu, China

Accepted May 05, 2021
Published May 08, 2021

*Corresponding Author:
Sheikh Sultan Ahmed
ovi143chad@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743833>

Pages: 34-41

Funding: There is no funding for this project

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
Ahmed, S. S., Rashed, K. N. (2021). Teaching Methodology and Use of Technology between China and Bangladesh: A Comparative Study. *North American Academic Research*, 4(5), 34-41.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743833>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

The educational stages in China is given bellow in Table 1.

Table 1. Educational stages in China

Educational Stages in China				
Typical age	Levels	Education	Grade/Class	Compulsory
18-22	Tertiary	University or College (Bachelor, Masters, PhD.)	Varies	No

ABSTRACT

This paper has shown how we can treat with modern technology in education system between Bangladesh and China. Few years back students did not find any interest in studies because of the way they were taught. But after the advent of technology the scenario has changed radically. Now the students can submit their assignments through internet, they can find suitable article, documents etc. Bangladeshi educational system is often criticized by the western observers, saying it cultivates students of higher score and law abilities. The Bangladeshi educational system is similar to English. Though there are different types of programs but here we just focused on basic educational system and technology. It would be interesting to compare the educational uses of technology between China and Bangladesh.

Keywords: BANGLADESHI EDUCATION, CHINESE EDUCATION, EDUCATION SYSTEM, TECHNOLOGY, METHODOLOGY.

Introduction

In China education system in 1980. The total nominal duration of primary and general secondary education was set at 12 years. Bachelor programs nominal is 4 years. Postgraduate master's program is 3 years. Adult education system is also significantly expanded. All private education institutions were either closed or converted. The Chinese education system is very centralized and it supervised by Ministry of Education. The education and official language is Mandarin. The academic year is September till June and consists of two 20-week semesters

15-17	Secondary	High School (senior middle school)/ Vocational school	Grades 10-12	No
12-14	Secondary	Junior Middle school	Grades 7-9	No
6-11	Primary	Primary School	Grades 1-7	No

Source: Authors' illustration

In Bangladesh education system is both formal and non-formal are available. The Ministry of Education (MoE) and the Ministry of Primary and Mass Education (MoPME) policy in control of all education system. This includes religious education (taught at Madrasah) technical and vocational education. The MoE prepares legislation and regulations drafts policies and carries out supervision of educational institution, The MoPME is responsible for primary education and non- formal education. University Grants Commission (UGC) plays an advisory and regulatory role of higher education in Bangladesh. (DSHE)The Directorate of Secondary and Higher Education is responsible for the administration of secondary schools (state schools and private schools), teacher training programs for secondary education and curriculum development for secondary education. The Bangladesh Technical Education Board (BTEB) is responsible for the development of technical and professional education. The educational stages in Bangladesh are given bellow in Table 1.

Table 2. Educational stages in Bangladesh

Educational Stages in Bangladesh				
Typical Age	Levels	University or College (Bachelor, Fazil, Masters/ Kamil, PhD)	Grade/ Class	Compulsory
18-25	Tertiary	Higher Secondary / Alim/ Vocational/ Diploma	Varies	No
16-17	Secondary	Secondary education/ Dakhil/ Vocational	Grades 11-12	No
14-15	Secondary	Junior Secondary education/ Dakhil	Grades 9-10	No
11-13	Secondary	Primary education/	Grades 6-8	No
6-10	Primary	Ebtedayee	Grade 1-5	No

Source: Authors' illustration

Education is a vital factor for the overall development of any country. The competitiveness of the 21st century compels higher education institutions to modernize their systems and practices. Nowadays, information and communications technology (ICT) bring a new set of challenges and pressures. There is a global trend in both educational policy and research to recognize the need to reform education from traditional paradigms of teaching and learning into more. Innovative forms of pedagogical practice. The demand for higher education has accelerated worldwide. Governments and universities are looking for innovative ways to increase access to higher education and improve the quality of their programs and courses. Regarding this, governments and education systems around the world take the use of technology in university very seriously. Bangladesh and

China, like many other countries, is investing greatly in the education system. At present technology not only play an important role in the classroom but also outside of the classroom. In this study, the importance of technology and the usage of the technologies to learners for both countries is analyzed. All the learning activity of the students through technology for China and Bangladesh has defined here.

The questions of this research are mentioned in the following sections;

- What are the differences teaching methodology and technology between China and Bangladesh?
- What are the similarities and dissimilarities teaching methodology and technology between China and Bangladesh?

In this study the modern technology in education system between Bangladesh and China is examined. This study encompassed the different sorts of devices which are used by the learners in both countries. So this study could contribute to enrich the proper use of technology in learning education system in Bangladeshi and Chinese context.

Literature review

Teaching methodology and use of technology between China and Bangladesh established that the technological devices can be a better outcome for the next step. Education is the key to overall development of a nation. This utilization exists among the fetter less government education policy creator in Bangladesh. Compared to international level of education in both China and Bangladesh system are not competitive and this has troublesome implicating upon the overall national development. Lack of a unified curriculum has been the bane of the education sector for the past 44 years in Bangladesh. it is time to rise above political agenda and make objective analytical studies of the prevailing situation in the education sector and identify weakness for remedy. This paper mainly focused at presents a critical analysis of education system of Bangladesh and provide way out to act upon. China has been a precursor in inclusive information and communication technologies for education all purposes (ICT4E) nationwide educational policies, present days the country has appeared as an international leader in propagating the benefits of ICT4E. At the levels of the school and individual learners, however ICT4E still play a subordinated role. China's education system is characterized by two basic worries. Firstly, while the system has expanded at all levels, enabling 40 percent of an age cohort to attend a university in 2017 (compared to 17 percent in 2003), schools and universities have increasingly diversified in quality and prestige. Various social and geographical divides impact the educational quality that students have access to, such as lower vs. middle class background or rural vs. urban residency. Secondly, while the curriculum reform since the late 1990s intends to turn Chinese students into creative, innovative, active, and responsible members of the knowledge society, persisting forms of examination that stress rote learning and cramming, such as the university entrance examination (gaokao 高考), run counter to these goals – as does continued political-ideological control Both in China and internationally, ICT4E have been associated with potential improvements

in teaching, learning, and educational administration. Throughout policy design and discussion, two questions have kept re-surfacing over the past 15 years. First, how to keep control of the content while making information and knowledge accessible for all; and second, how to strike a balance between involving private and commercial actors while keeping the state in the driver's seat. Already in 2002, the Ministry of Education (MOE) made it clear that online content should be "healthy, reliable and secure;" it also cautioned against an over-emphasis on commercial interests.⁶ However, there is little detail on the regulation and standardization of online content in education, and the issue has largely been left to the general censorship and control mechanisms (such as the Great Firewall). More recently, plans have emerged to combine ICT4E with moral education and the cultivation of "good citizens;" besides, "security" (of technology and content) has lately been added as a focus of attention.⁷ Regarding commercial actors, the Chinese government stresses that unlike "Western countries" it does not rely primarily on the market but follows the principle of "government policies controlling, companies participating in the construction, and schools using sustainably" ICT4E.⁸ Again, lack of regulatory clarity leaves a grey zone in which commercial actors can operate. ICT4E policies in the Xi Jinping era are marked by the following four characteristics: Education as a shared resource. "Enjoying together" is a key term in education (and beyond) in the 13th Five-Year-Plan (2016-2020).⁹ Tackling the problem of both quality and equality in education, Xi Jinping intends to "let millions of children enjoy high-quality education;" through ICT4E, "all people can learn, people can learn everywhere, and people can learn at any time," enabling everyone to "change one's destiny through knowledge."¹⁰ Re-centralization of ideology through education. The Xi Jinping administration also places increased emphasis on moral education as a root to national wellbeing. This marks a shift from the previous emphasis on learner autonomy and creativity towards more ideological control of the curriculum. Offline, these efforts have included the recentralized production of textbooks and strengthened ideology education; online, security concerns begin to be addressed more systematically in ICT4E strategies. Investment in mass innovation. While ICT4E have long been associated with innovation and creativity, the Xi Jinping administration has reinforced the mission of nurturing and spreading "innovation" in various announcements and guidelines. The administration's focus is on expanding innovation from the elites to the masses, by facilitating grassroots innovation. ICT, both in education and beyond, are considered to play an important role in this mission. Policy papers do not address the potential contradiction between calls for innovation and creativity on the one hand and increasing ideological control on the other. Push for global impact through education. China's ICT4E strategy also has a global dimension that has been substantially expanded under Xi Jinping. As has been noted by UNESCO, 11 China has been able to distinguish itself as an important global actor in ICT4E particularly in Africa. Also, the UNESCO International Research and Training Centre for Rural Education, which has a strong focus on ICT4E, is based in Beijing. Underlining his personal investment in the issue, Xi delivered the welcome address at the International Conference on ICT and Post-2015 Education, jointly organized with UNESCO, in May 2015 in Qingdao. This conference resulted in the so-called Qingdao Declaration of "Leveraging ICTs for Achieving Education 2030" as well as in a series of follow-up conferences in Qingdao and internationally. On the other hand, Bangladeshi education system is divided into three levels,

Primary level (class 1–8) Secondary level (9–12): There is no middle school system in Bangladesh. Tertiary level. Education in Bangladesh is overseen by the country's Ministry of Education. The Ministry of Primary and Mass Education is responsible for implementing policy for primary education and state-funded schools at a local level. In Bangladesh, all citizens must undertake twelve years of compulsory education which consists of eight years at primary school level and four years at high school level. Primary and secondary education is financed by the state and free of charge in public schools. Bangladesh conforms fully to the UN's Education For All (EFA) objectives [3] and the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) [4] as well as other education-related international declarations.

Materials and methods

This is an illustrative and methodical research based on use of technology in education. It is essential to trace the origin and development of the usage of technology in learning and teaching process in the area of legal education. Importance, has been given to sort out the most useful and meaningful ways of technologies to be used in teaching and learning.

Results

Modern learning theory directs the use of technological tools to prepare students in the real as well as practical world settings to meet the up-to-date challenges. Some law classrooms in some universities in Bangladesh now have sophisticated technology. The issue that most researchers ask is whether technology can empower legal teaching in Bangladesh. Some law Professors in Bangladesh are very keen in using educational technology. For effective legal education, technological skills are required in analyzing legal problems, performing legal research, collecting, sorting facts, and writing effectively. Such may include the use of quantitative and qualitative software's like statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) for data analysis. Ironically, in many countries, especially, in Bangladesh and China also some other South-Asian countries have a very common misconception regarding the use of modern technology. The studies main focus on teaching methodology and use of technology between China and Bangladesh. Its an important key point that can be realize for country.

Importance of technology in future

Technology in near future will prevail and dominate in almost all the aspects of teaching method areas. The researchers have observed that within a very short span of time technology and artificial intelligence will be used in many sectors of teaching areas.²⁴ Technology will unquestionably be a key factor in how education in the future differs from education today. The Chinese central government's enthusiastic embrace of ICT4E has led to a myriad of initiatives and platforms, operated by both state and commercial actors. In areas where political leaders encourage ICT4E initiatives, this has led to an uneconomical competition of various projects, at times producing wasteful duplicates; while in less focused regions, there can be a lack of commitment to ICT4E altogether. Another side effect of the massive investment in ICT4E is the urgency to spend the allocated resources. Even more problematic is the social acceptance of ICT4E among teachers and families. Fieldwork

conducted by the author in the years 2014 to 2017 showed that most teachers and parents regard Modern learning Technology as inadequate for learning. They consider ICT as distracting and potentially counter-productive for children, and at the school as well as in family homes, ICT are at best offered for entertainment and relaxation, often as reward after long periods of cramming and rote learning. These latter, conventional modes of learning are considered most efficient for attaining good exam results. In fact, schools' higher performance often corresponds to a less frequent use of Learning methodology.

China is a learner and a leader in learning methodology:

China's heavy investment in Modern and teaching methodology does not only have domestic implications but is also of global relevance. Many observers regard China primarily as a learner as an emerging nation that, in the field of education, needs to solve above all two issues: equal access to high-quality education across regions and schools; and upgrading the country to an innovative knowledge society, in order to be a creator, and not just a maker, of globally competitive products. Teaching methods are seen to help in this quest. However, China has also emerged as a global actor in (offline) education, and the government's ambitions have moved beyond learning from other countries and reforming its own system. International large-scale assessments of educational performance such as PISA have shown the competitiveness of (some parts of) the Chinese school system. This has not only resulted in educational publications to market the Chinese solution to the rest of the world, but also to the actual export of teaching experiences and models to developed countries like the United Kingdom an achievement that the Chinese MOE has been particularly proud of.²⁷ For the most part, these exports have focused on conventional methods of teaching and learning with the aim to achieve excellence. This involves educational aid to, and engagement in, developing countries, particularly in Africa.³⁰ China increases its export of Teaching method like ICT technologies and know-how to Africa,³¹ and it has intensified its ICT4E engagement on the African continent. Cultural Soft Power Research Center at Peking University³⁴ – these global activities suggest that China is ready to assume global leadership in education.

Conclusion

In Bangladesh, technology offers an attractive possibility of making ability in education more efficient and more effective both for the teachers and the students. Usage of technology can make education flexible and interesting. The primary purpose of both the traditional and technological legal education in the real-life context is to provide a space in which the facilitation of learning, and learning itself, can take place and be more successful to the truest meaning of success. It is true that one of the ultimate goals of multimedia legal education in Bangladesh is to promote students' motivation and learning interest. In near future, the use of multimedia in legal education will be further developed, especially, in the universities of Bangladesh. Also, Chinese School, colleges and universities are more advance about Modern technology uses in teaching methodology. The process of teaching and learning of law by using technology makes the overall process more student-oriented but less time-consuming. Therefore, it promises that the teaching excellence will be enhanced and the practical

law skills of students can be efficiently cultivated. To assure and realize an efficient result of teaching method and learning by using technology is no more a day dream or nightmare.

References

- 1) Becker, H. J. (2000). Access to classroom computers. *Communications of the ACM*.
- 2) Burkhard, S. (2001). Legal transplants and legal downloads. *International review Law*.
- 3) Cownie, F. (2005). The liberal law school in the 21st century. *McGill law journal*.
- 4) Chesterman, S. (2008). The globalization of legal education. *Singapore journal of legal education*.
- 5) Garson, G.D. (2007). *Modern public information technology systems: Issues and challenges*. Hershey, PA: IGI Publishing.
- 6) Germanian, C. (2007). Legal information management in a global and digital age:
- 7) Revolution and tradition. *Cornell legal studies Research papers*.
- 8) Goldman, P. (2008). Legal Education and Technology. *Law library journal*.
- 9) Meyer, H. (2008). Extreme Makeover. *ABA journal*, 94(2).
- 10) Murray, K. (2007). My e- semester: New uses for technology in the legal research and working classroom. *Research studies*, 15(3), 194.
- 11) Pedersen, L.T. (2002). Trends in legal education in the learning society- the challenges of information technology. *International journal of the legal profession*.
- 12) Note that many of these assumptions have proven problematic or simplistic upon implementation; see e.g. the critique in Lankshear and Knobel (2008) and OECD (2015, 2017).
- 13) Esarey, A. (2015). "Winning hearts and minds? Cadres as microbloggers in China." In: *Journal of Current Chinese Affairs*, 44(2), 69-103.
- 14) Ministry of Education (2012). "教育部关于印发《教育信息化十年发展规划(2011-2020)》的通知。” (Ten Year Development Plan for the Information of Education (Years 2011-2020).
- 15) Ministry of Education (2002). "教育部关于推进教师教育信息化建设的意见” (The Ministry of Education's opinion regarding the establishment of an informatization of teacher education).
- 16) See the statement by the Vice Minister of Education: Du, Zhanyuan (2017). "发展教育信息化。推动教育现代化 2030“ (Developing the informatization of education. Pushing educational modernization 2030).
- 17) Mahmud, A., Ding, D., & Hasan, M. M. (2021). Corporate social responsibility: Business responses to Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. *SAGE Open*, 11(1), 2158244020988710.
- 18) Guangxi Education (2017). "Embracing 'Internet Plus:' forcefully pushing the modernization of education." In: *Guangxi Jiaoyu*, No. 24.
- 19) Ministry of Education (2017 a). "关于印发教育部副部长杜占元在2017年全国教育信息化工作会议上讲话的通知” (On the announcement published by the Ministry of Education regarding the speech by the vice minister of education Du Zhanyuan at a work meeting on the country's informatization in 2017).

- 20) Mahmud, A., Ding, D., Kiani, A., & Hasan, M. M. (2020). Corporate Social Responsibility Programs and Community Perceptions of Societal Progress in Bangladesh: A Multimethod Approach. *SAGE Open*, 10(2), 2158244020924046.
- 21) Ministry of Education (2017 a). “关于印发教育部副部长杜占元在2017年全国教育信息化工作会议上讲话的通知” (On the announcement published by the Ministry of Education regarding the speech by the vice minister of education Du Zhanyuan at a work meeting on the country’s informatization in 2017). May5 教技司 No.157.http://www.moe.gov.cn/s78/A16/s8213/A16_sjhj/201709/t20170911_314154.html. Accessed May 17, 2018.
- 22) Hasan, M., & Mahmud, A. (2017). Risks management of ready-made garments industry in Bangladesh. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 10(1), 1-13.
- 23) http://www.moe.gov.cn/srcsite/A16/s3342/201606/t20160622_269367.html. Accessed: May 22, 2018.
- 24) Xinhua News (2015). “Xi Jinping sends letter to congratulate on the opening of the international conference on the informatization of education.” May 23. *Zhongguo Jiaoyu Wangluo*, 6, 11.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

